

1 **Function of the viral protein Tat in B-cells.**

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6 Tat has functions in viremia and latency. We measured total transcription in B-cell cultures following
7 ectopic expression of the viral gene Tat. Tat altered the epigenetic status of the cell (*Tfec* and *Bzw2*
8 induction with silencing of *Bhlehe22*). Tat m dysregulated Fc receptor expression (*Fcgr2a*). Expression of
9 Tat activated the interferon response (*Mx1*) but altered the immune state of the cell (*Aldh4a1*). Tat
10 expression resulted in induction of chemokines and chemokine receptors including *CCL3*, *CCL3L3* and
11 *CCL4*. Tat could silence *Lin28b* *in vitro*.

12 Citations

13 1. Allen, T.M., O'Connor, D.H., Jing, P., Dzuris, J.L., Mothé, B.R., Vogel, T.U., Dunphy, E., Liebl,
14 M.E., Emerson, C., Wilson, N. and Kunstman, K.J., 2000. Tat-specific cytotoxic T lymphocytes select for
15 SIV escape variants during resolution of primary viraemia. *Nature*, 407(6802), pp.386-390.

16 GSE233499

17 GSE212499

18 GSE182538